

Effect of Parental Involvement on Learning Outcomes of Upper Primary Students

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Abstract

This research paper is undertaken to study the effect of parental involvement on learning outcomes of upper primary school students in Ghaziabad district. This study was conducted on a sample of 240 students and their parents selected from rural and urban area of district. The Parental Involvement test developed by Rita Chopra and Surbala Sahoo was administrated for collecting data. The statistical techniques for data analysed were used. The finding of study revealed that there is a significant effect of parental involvement on learning outcomes of upper primary students.

Introduction

The overall development of a child is the key factor of education system. Teacher and parents both are committed for their child's education. Parents are primary teacher of a child and they involved consistently in the progress of their children. According to smith (2011) Parental involvement is the commitment from the parents to actively participate in both the school and their children education. It is said that if parent are more involved in their ward's learning activities, in schools had higher effect on learning outcomes of childrens. But today when some parents are working and busy in other activities they had no enough time to participated in school activities of their child' learning. Therefore it is important to examine factors that had effects on learning outcomes of children through parental involvement. Key words -Parental Involvement, learning outcomes.

Objectives of the Study

The study has been designed to find out following objectives :-

1. To study the effect of parental involvement on learning outcomes of urban and rural school students at upper-primary.
2. To study effect of parental involvement on learning outcomes of boys and girls students at upper primary.

Hypothesis of the study

The null hypothesis have been formulated to obtain the objectives of the study.

1. There is no significance difference between high and low parental involvements of urban students at upper primary schools.
2. There is no significance difference between high and low parental involvement of rural students at upper-primary schools.
3. There is no significance difference between boys and girls having high and low parental Involvement at upper primary schools.
4. There is no relationship between learning outcomes of rural and urban students having high and low parental involvement.

Delimitation of the study

This study will be confined to-

1. Students of government schools.
2. Students of V to VIII class at upper primary schools.
3. Students of Ghaziabad city.

Review of the Study : The present paper aims to analyse the relationship between parental involvement in school and learning outcomes of students of upper primary schools. It has been suggested through many researcher that if parents are involved a student may see the importance of study that lead them to high in life.

Griffth J. (1996) organized a study on the relation of parental involvement and students academic performance of elementary school level. The study focused on the school characteristics such as class size, strength and capacity. The performance of students measured through criterion reference test. The study pointed out a positive and significant

relationship between parental involvement and empowerment but real participation of parents was not discussed in schools.

Ho Sui Chu (1997) investigated a study on parental academic Involvement as related to behaviour, achievement and aspirations of students. The study revealed that parents with more education status tend to more involved with their children's schooling and had higher education aspirations. In this study researcher suggested for further areas of intervention that determined factors of parental involvement.

Amant and Deslandes (1998) investigated a study of family variables as predictors of school achievement. The study addressed the gender differences of students at secondary level on their achievement outcomes. In the study there were 525 participants of age group of 14-16 of girls and boys in a region of Quebec. Researcher found a significant difference in affective supports to their sons than daughters.

Zellman and Waterman (1998) revealed important contributions of parent participation in Child's learning. This study suggests that parent are predicator of learning outcomes of their children while they are more involved at school. The positive parenting style may be a most encouraging factor to help their children at learning outcomes. The researcher focused on five measures of parent school involvement, attendance at school events participation in school activities, and P.T.A. meetings.

Fan & Chan (1999) organized a study on parental involvement and students academic achievement of students. This study revealed out a positive relationship with parental involvement and students academic achievement. This study demonstrated different dimensions of parental involvement separately at home with academic aspirations.

Marcon (1999) investigated a study on impact of parental involvement on Children's development and academic performance. This study revealed that positive outcomes for pre- school children depended a threshold of parent involvement. The study pointed out that highly involved parents had high effect in development and academic performance than a minimum involvement needed to behaviour of pre-school children. The researcher did not found significant relationship based on six families status or single parent's condition.

Mimrot BH (2016) organized a study of academic achievement relation to home environment of secondary school students. The study found the positive relationship between academic achievement environment and home environment of students in Private and Govt. schools. Home environment scale by Dr. Karuna Shankar Mishra was used for collect data.

The result revealed a significant positive relationship between home environment and academic achievement. The statistical method was 't' ratio. The finding of study has implication for both parents and teachers.

Martinez A (2015) organized a study on parental involvement and its effects on student academic achievement. The purpose of this study was to find out differences between english, arts and mathematics achievement of fourth grade students that parents were Involved in school's activities. The sample of 30 students has taken for study. The statistical method 't' test was used for scoring. The result of study suggested that highly involved parents had positive effect on academic achievement of students.

Research Methodology

This study was quantitative in nature and descriptive survey method was used. The data collected through simple random technique. The percentile technique was used for to show relationship between learning outcomes high and low parental Involvement of urban and rural students. For statistical analysis 't' test was used.

Data Collection : In this study data was collected from 240 students studying in upper primary and their parents of class VI to VIII. The government schools were selected of Ghaziabad district. The proper Instruction were given to parents and students for tool administration.

Tool : Parental Involvement scale by Dr Rita Chopra and Surbala Sahoo was used for data collection. This tool has three dimension but the researcher used total involvement for his study. For learning outcomes student's score card was subjected to statistical analysis.

Data Analysis : After administration of tool data was divided in high to low. The first $\frac{1}{4}$ higher most were considered as high parental involvement and the last $\frac{1}{4}$ lower most were considered as low parental involvement. The score of parental involvement were arrange in high and low parental involvement transferred to a master sheet. So the final analysis contain sample of 30 urban and 30 rural students and their parents and 30 boys and 30 girls students. The data organized on a sheet was subjected of the test of significance i.e. 't' test.

After statistical analysis of data the result has been presented and interpreted in following Tables.

Table I Mean difference of urban students having high and low parental involvement on learning outcomes.

Groups	N	Mean	SD	't' ratio
High parental Involvement	30	73.17	2.78	27.73
Low parental Involvement	30	56.17	1.90	

Table I Shows that there is significance different between high and low parental Involvement of urban students. The null hypothesis has been rejected both of level .05 and .01. It reveals that there exits significance difference between low parental involvement of urban school towards learning outcomes.

Table II : Mean difference of rural student having, high and low parental Involvement on learning outcomes.

Groups	N	Mean	SD	't' ratio
High parental Involvement	30	64.32	2.72	20.77
Low parental Involvement	30	52.17	1.72	

Above table II shows that the value of 't' is 20.77 which is found to be highly significant at both level .05 and .01. It means that there is a significant difference between rural student having high and low parental involvement towards learning outcomes. Thus null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference rural students having high and low parental involvement rejected both level .05 and .01.

Table III: Mean difference of boys of upper primary school having high and low parental Involvement on learning outcomes.

Groups	N	Mean	SD	't' ratio
High parental Involvement	30	82.16	5.96	11.68
Low parental Involvement	30	56.23	10.62	

The result (table III) shows that obtained 't' value is 11.68 which is found to be significant at both .05 and .01 level. It means that there is significance difference between boys of upper primary schools having high and low parental Involvement towards learning outcomes. Thus the null hypothesis has been rejected both of levels.

Table IV: Mean difference of Girls of upper primary school having high and low parental Involvement towards learning outcomes.

Groups	N	Mean	SD	't'ratio
High parental Involvement	30	78.4	4.63	12.86
Low parental Involvement	30	62.83	4.82	

The table IV shows that the obtained 't' ratio is 12.86 which is highly significance at both .05 and .01 level. It means there is significance difference between girls at upper- primary school having high and low parental Involvement towards learning outcomes. Thus null hypothesis has been rejected both of levels.

Table V: Learning outcomes of urban and rural students having high and low parental Involvement.

Learning outcomes	Urban students		rural students	
	High parental Involvement	Low parental Involvement	High parental Involvement	Low parental Involvement
Scores (%)				
80-100	10	4	2	Nil
60-79	18	22	15	15
Below 60	2	4	15	5

Graphical Representation:-

In table V and graphical presentation of learning outcomes of high and low parental involvement clearly shows that high parental involvement has high influence on their score. While low parental involvement of urban and rural students reflect as low score. So it is interpreted that high parental involvement of urban and rural students has a effective influence on learning outcomes positively at upper primary schools.

Conclusion:- from above presented result of Tables I to V and graphs of learning outcomes (score) of students, it was concluded that parental involvement of urban and rural boys and girls students has a positive influence on learning outcomes of upper primary students. The

major finding of this study is that high parental involvement enhances learning outcomes positively.

Recommendation and Suggestion : The following are some primary recommendations based on the finding from this study.

- The research should be carried out on large sample.
- There is a need to fill the gap between parent and teacher for betterment of students learning.
- A new approach of effective parental Involvement in government schools should be mechanism through school management committees and Parent- TeacherAssociations.
- Every parent should be oriented about the needs of changing world, society and psychological needs of their wards for proper development.
- Parents should try to develop a educational atmosphere in the home and involve their school activities, so that they understand their educational needs and sort out these.
- Parents should act as a facilitator for students learning.
- Understanding and accepting vital of effective parental involvement, the government and private sector should emphasizes for creating good and satisfied environment for parents.
- Parental involvement in school- related matters is an effective means of helping the students to become accountable to self and parents. Students in this age groups feel highly motivated when their parents share some of this enthusiasm.
- Parental Involvement contributes to academic well being of student, values and life issues so that they can shape the future of nation.
- The researcher has included urban and rural school students of government sector. It may also be studied in private sector and higher education sector.
- There are many other factors that influence learning outcomes of students which yet have to be identified and studied.
- Instead of ‘t’ test researcher may use factorial design of analysis and correlation methods for interpretation of data.

Reference:-

- Catsambis, Sophia : Expanding the knowledge of parental Involvement in Secondary Education : Effects on High School Academic Success. Report No. 27, Non Journal Pages 41 1998 – Dec. ERIC Number : ED426174 National Inst. on the Education of At-risk Students (ED/OERI). Washington, D.C.
- Deslandes Rollande : Bouchard, Pierette; St-Amant, Jean-Claude : Family Variables as predictors of school Achievement : Sex Differences in Quebec : Adolescents, Canadian Journal of Education, Vol. 23 N 4, P 390-404 1998. ERIC Number-EJ 596340 ISSN-0380-2361.
- Fan & Chen M. Parental involvement and students, academic achievement : meta- analysis, Educational psychology review : 13 (1) : (1-22)
- Griffth. J (1996) : Relation of Parental Involvement, Empowerment, and School traits to Student academic performance. Journal of Educational Research, Vol. 90 P 33-41 Sept.-Oct. 1996 ERIC Number : EJ538470.
- Gonzalez-De Hass AR, Willems PP, Holbein MF. Examining the relationship between parental involvement and student motivation. Educational psychology Review.2005;17:99-123.
- Georgiou S. N. : Parental attributions as predictors of involvement and influences on child achievement. British Journal of Educational Psychology, (Wiley Online Library) 69 (3), 409-429 1999.
- Ho Sui-chu E. And Willian, J.D. : Effects of Parental Involvement of Eight-Grade Achievement. Sociology of Education Vol. 69, No 2 (Apr-1996 PP. 126-141 Published by : American Sociological Association DOI : 10.2307/.2112802 <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2112802> Page Count : 16.
- Hara SR, Burks DJ. Parent involvement : The key to improved student achievement. The School Community Journal.1998;8:9-19.
- Hill NE, Craft SA. Parent -School involvement and school performance : Mediated pathways among socioeconomically comparable African families. Journal of Educational Psychology. 2003; 96 : 74-83.
- Kohl GO, Lengua LJ. Mc Mohan R.J. - Parent Involvement in school : Conceptualizing multiple dimensions and their relations with family and demographic risk factors. Journal of School Psychology. 2000;38:501-523.

- Mimrot B. H. : A study of academic achievement relation to home environment of secondary school students. International Journal of India Psychology-2006 4 (1) : 30- 40.
- Martinez A : Parental involvement and its effects on student academic achievement (Master's thesis, California State University, Stanislaus), 2015.
- Marcon R.A. : Impact of Parent Involvement on Children's Development and Academic Performance : A Three-Cohort Study-Report-Research, speeches/Meeting Papers P. No. 9 1999-March ERIC Number, ED 4278 80.
- Mimrot B. H. : A Study of Academic Achievement Environment Relation to Home Environment of Secondary School Students. International Journal of Indian Psychology, Vol-4 (1) : 30-40 Dec-2016 DOI : 10.25 215/401.084.
- Martinez A : Parental Involvement and its effects on student academic achievement (Master's Thesis, California State University, Stanislaus 2015.
- Smith Y. K. : Impact of parental involvement on students achievement (Doctoral dissertation, University of Southern California) 2011.
- Verma P. Raina G. : Quality of parental relationship enjoyed by the students public schools of Shimla, Journal of Community Guidance and Research 2016, 33 (1) : 171- 181.

